

Mal-Vision: Intelligent early malaria prediction system

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Abstract:

Malaria is the deadliest disease in the earth and big hectic work for the health department. The traditional way of diagnosing malaria is by schematic examining blood smears of human beings for parasite-infected red blood cells under the microscope by lab or qualified technicians. Malaria is a parasitic infection caused in humans by the parasite belonging to the genus Plasmodium. The traditional approach of diagnosis by the use of microscopy, considered to be the “gold standard method” has at times proved to be inefficacious and inefficient as it is time consuming, needs more expertise and is erring at times. This raises a need for better alternatives for the diagnosis of the parasitic infection. This paper highlights the advancement in the field of machine learning and its beneficial applications in the detection, identification and diagnosis of the malarial infection via the use of smartphones. It uses a pre trained CNN for the detection of the parasite. The experimental results excelled in the relevant attributes of accuracy, efficiency and sensitivity of this technique, making this outperform the traditional means of detection.

Keywords: *Malaria Detection, Machine learning, deep learning, image processing, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Feature extraction, Classification algorithms.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI), which is based on machine learning and deep learning, is becoming more and more well-liked and accepted in the fields of medicine and healthcare due to its ability to outperform people, notably in the recognition and interpretation of images. There are five

species which infect humans namely *P. falciparum*, *P. malariae*, *P. vivax*, *P. ovale* and *P. knowlesi*. Out of the five species, the *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* possess a fatal infection consequence. The first ever case of malaria was detected and discovered in 1870's ever since which the disease has been a prominent cause of death in most of the Sub-Saharan African region with a rise of 90% cases annually as of the year 2020. According to the UNICEF annual survey, the malaria accounts for 1 million deaths and around 300-600 million people diagnosed per year. India is also predominantly affected by the parasitic infection with 15 million cases registered annually according to the World Health Organization. The disease spreads by the bite of the female *Anopheles* mosquito species, commonly known as mosquito vectors. The mechanism of infection involves the spread of sporozoites through the salivary glands of the mosquito into the bloodstream. Even after the defeasance by the immune system, some of these sporozoites succeed in affecting the hepatocytes. The infection spreads by reproduction and multiplication of these parasites inside. Some of the most common symptoms include fever, chills, fatigue, nausea and headache. Some of the severe cases with fatal infection can also result in jaundice, coma or death of the infected individual. The detection and diagnosis of malaria parasitic infection is even more necessary to be efficient, reliable and accurate in order for us to tackle the endemic and control or reduce the number of deaths annually. The "gold standard method" used for the diagnosis involves the manual assessment through microscopy. This is one of the oldest approaches and is highly reasonable, reliable and cost efficient. Though this method is considered to be achievable, it has certain obvious drawbacks. The manual approach of diagnosis is considerably time consuming as it has a number of steps for conducting the tests. It is also very much prone to human errors even when conducted by expert individuals in microscopy. Moreover, in places such as the Sub-Saharan African regions, due to the economic conditions, there might be a lack of such facilities. This raises a requirement to search for other alternatives for the diagnosis of malaria keeping the efficiency, the consistency, the accuracy, the sensitivity and the specificity as some of the relevant attributes. This paper establishes the importance towards the new approach of diagnosing the disease, that is, through the use of machine learning. The parasitic detection using semi-automated diagnosis increases the efficiency as well as the consistency of the tests. The applications of deep learning which include models such as the ANN and the CNN have various advantages over the manual testing and diagnosis. This paper briefly introduces the concept of machine learning and how it can be thoughtfully applied for the detection of the malaria through the blood samples. The concept has taken smartphones into account which will act as a handy, reliable, mobile and easily accessible tool for the detection in contrast to the microscopes or the Rapid Diagnosis Kits. The approach described is very much practical for the use in the clinics, hospitals or even by individuals at home. It requires minimal basic training. The digitization of the entire process increases the efficiency, accuracy and consistency to a greater value.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Ahmedelmubarak Bashir, Zeinab A. Mustafa, Islah Abdelhameid, Rimaz (2017) This paper, highlighting the drawbacks of the traditional ways of detecting malarial infection in cells through microscopy, focuses on the new advancements in the diagnosis through the application of Digital Image processing. They focused on the relevant features of the plasmodium as well as the erythrocytes. The features help distinguish between the infected and non-infected cells in the

sample by the evaluation and processing carried out by an Artificial Neural Network. The classification and detection of the plasmodium was done by putting ANN (Artificial Neural Network) to work. The accuracy of the system was found to be 99.68%. While designing these testing procedure key points from this paper was kept in mind. Mahdieh Poostchi, Kamolrat Silamut, Richard Maude, Stefan Jaeger, George Thoma (2017), The main objective of the paper involves the reviewing of certain recent developments in the technologies such as machine learning algorithms and deep learning techniques applied to smartphones and other devices and how they can be applied for the malarial infection diagnosis. It briefly explained the mechanism and working of the microscopy and highlighted the drawbacks. Likewise, it has also briefed the reader about the various types of stains being applied to the different types of microscopy including fluorochrome staining procedure but stating the drawbacks alone. The paper has also mentioned the recent advancements in the approach of using smartphones for diagnosis of malaria, mentioning several papers along with their applications. In conclusion, the paper gives an overview of the current advancements and helps the readers understand the applications of machine learning, deep learning as well as smart phones as potential approaches for the detection of the infection.

3. METHODOLOGY

Five major factors were kept in mind while designing the application. They are as follow: -

- 1) Modularity: The algorithm is created in a way that allows it to do multiple jobs. According to the user's needs it can identify various sickness or disease types.
- 2) Cost to the Consumer: Depending on the type of test and the area where it is conducted, the average cost might range from 60 to 360 rupees. In comparison to rural areas, costs in cities are comparably low. Therefore, everyone must be able to afford the testing process.
- 3) Reusability: The market already has fast testing kits, which cost about 36 rupees per test and are relatively portable. The sole disadvantage of such a kit is that it generates waste plastic and can only be used for one test. This issue can be resolved by digitizing every step of the testing process using this approach.
- 4) Simple Interface: A practical, dependable, portable, and conveniently available tool for the detection must have a user-friendly interface. When it comes to operators, the produced algorithm doesn't require any kind of particular specialization.
- 5) Compact and Mobile: The testing procedure must be small and portable so that it may be taken to various locations with ease. The entire testing process has been digitalized, allowing us to conduct tests at anytime and anywhere.

A. System Overview

A Smartphone (Small camera-equipped computing devices) is attached to a magnifying device which allows the true optical magnification of the sample to detect the parasite automatically,

using image detection and machine learning. Android phones are relatively cheap and most of the people already possess one. In the Image acquisition step, a multi-scale Laplacian of Gaussian filter is applied. As we don't have much to detect from the color of the image acquired, it is then converted into a Gray scale image. In order to improve the quality of the image and to reduce the variations in the images, it was important to remove the noise, improve the contrast, illumination and staining. To remove the noise Gaussian Blur filter is used. Due to the image being in Gray scale it normalizes the image illumination. The white blood cells being a larger in shape as compared to the red blood cells make their segregation much easier. But we intend to identify the white blood cells and not to process or classify it further. The detection of the parasite is important than the segregation of the blood cell. Therefore, the image is passed through Otsu threshold in combination with morphological operations followed by edge detection in order to detect the red blood cells and so the parasite. The parasites being stained, color features are most prominent and can be used for the detection. The idea is simple, in case of infected cells; these features appear to be in ring like structures with visible cytoplasm and unique parasite characteristics. The image is passed to contour detection filter of feature extraction which can detects such structures. A non-infected human cell should have only one contour i.e. no infection in the cell on the other hand if the cell is infected it will develop some pigmentation inside the human cell and hence resulting in formation of contour more than one.

Using this principle, based on the no of contour formed the image is segregated, if the number of contours is 1, it flags the cell un infected. And if the no. of contour is more than 1 then it passes the image through an CNN Algorithm which predicts whether the cell is infected by malaria or not.

4. ALGORITHM IMPLEMENTATION

Processes in Algorithm implementation: -

A. Image Acquisition

B. RBG to Gray Conversion

1. Patients are interrogated, and the information gathered is kept in a patient file.
2. The use of mydriatic eye drops. Each eye receives a drop of Fotorretin (Phenylephrine 5% and Tropicamide 0,5% Laboratory Poen, Argentina) every 15 minutes for a total of two applications. The examination is conducted with the Visucam 500 camera in a dark room after 30 minutes,

when pupil dilation is complete [1]. In order to properly support the forehead and chin, the patient must be seated in front of the apparatus.

3. Using a Visucam 500 camera by Zeiss, an image of the retina is taken from each eye.

4. After that, a fundoscopic examination is carried out using a 20D magnifier and an indirect ophthalmoscope. The patient's file contains information about the diabetic retinopathy's stage. In the analysis of the acquired retinographies, the out-of-focus images, with artifacts or with low image quality due to media opacity (presence of corneal scars, cataracts, or vitreous opacities such as hemovitreal or vitritis), are discarded. Patients with other concurrent retinal disease are excluded from retinal imaging studies.[25]

3.2. Preprocessing and Augmentation

Due to range of camera devices used, the fundus-photographs of the data set differed in shape, resolution-color, making it necessary for preprocessing the images in order to artificially compact the commonness. Differences in intrinsic feature distributions were lessened with the use of preprocessing. All photos were first scaled down to 512x512 pixels. On each channel, the three processes below were consecutively applied in order to remove the overall outputted tone, brightness, variance between pictures. After calculating the Z-score, the inner image minimum-maximum normalization was performed with the aim of converting the grayscale values to a scale from 0 to 255.

3.2.1. Enhancement

Digital pictures are modified during the image enhancement process to provide results that are better suitable for presentation or further picture analysis. The original range of grey levels is widened by the linear transformation, resulting in contrast augmentation or stretching as shown in figure 3.

FIGURE 3: Retinal image enhancement process

Spatial filtering enhances lineaments, faults, and shear zones are examples of naturally occurring linear features. Differentiated features are represented by a series of density intervals, each of which is identified by a different color or symbol, using a technique called density slicing.

3.3. Model Evaluation by CNN Architecture

The architecture of the trainable multi-stages made of various stages can be used to define this type of neural network. Each stage's inputs and outputs are sets of arrays known as feature maps. Each feature map for the outputs represents a distinct feature that was taken from every place that was on the input. Three layers make up each stage; a filter-collection, a nonlinearity-level, and a layer of pool feature. Three layers or fewer are required for a classic (CNN). The modules for classification come after these first three tiers. The image recognition case's several layers are described as follows.

3.3.1. Input Layer

The input layer establishes the shape of any supplied pictures in the CNN. Additionally, it includes the raw pixel values for the image. The image size is determined by the input image's width, height, and number of color channels. For example, there is only one channel for grayscale photos and three for color images. The mean or median of the image in the training dataset is subtracted from each input image by the input level for normalizing the data.

3.3.2. Convolutional-2D Layer

Neurons of this layer are related of various areas of input or output pictures from the layer below. While scanning over the photos, this layer can pick up on any feature that is localized using these regions. A variety of weight sets that may be applied to a specific part of the image were employed in this layer. The input image could be moved vertically and horizontally along the entire filter. For each area, the inputs are convolved again in this phase using the same method. This step's length with its movements is called a stride. These local regions to which the associated neurons have connections may overlap based on the Stride's value and the filter-Size. $w*h*c$ is the weights number used in the filter. c is channel number in the input image and w and h are the sizes of each filter, respectively. In this case, the example channel for color photos is 3. The channel Convolutional layer output number can be determined by the filter number. The comparable weights set and convolution are used, as was previously discussed, to create the map as the filters traverse through the input images. As a result, the number of channels in the feature maps for this layer is the same. Each feature map has its own distinctive collection of biases and weights. Consequently, the convolutional layer's total parameter count is $((w*h* c + 1)* \text{Filters Number})$. Padding should also be mentioned in this layer. In essence, it is tallied by bordering the input image with zero columns or rows. Controlling the output size of the layer can be beneficial. The output layer's height and width can then be calculated using the formula in equation 1.

$$(\text{Input Shape} - \text{Filter Shape} + 2 \text{ times Padding}) / \text{Stride} + 1. \quad (1)$$

3.3.3. Batch Normalization

To speed up network training and lessen the sensitivity of network initialization, these layers can be utilized in combination with convolution and ReLU layers. The layer normalizes the activation by deducting the small batch average and for each channel and dividing the result by mini batch SD. It executes shift using offset after the input scaling using a scaling factor. The variables are thought of as trainable that can be changed. In a neural network, this layer normalizes gradient activations and their propagation. This is done to help with the network training's optimization issue. This layer can be used to increase learning rate to the fullest extent.

3.3.4. Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) Layer

A nonlinear activation function, in this case a (ReLU) layer, specifically a "rectified linear unit" layer, is typically followed by convolution and batch normalization layers. Using this layer, every element is exposed to threshold operations, and every negative input value is equalized to zero, as in equation 2.

$$f(x) = \max(0, x). \quad (2)$$

3.3.5. Max Pool Layers

Layers are placed after any convolutional-2D layer to down sample. This is employed to reduce number of connections to following levels. These layers don't function for self-learning purposes. Lowering the number of variables to be trained can reduce over fitting in subsequent levels. The max pool layers return the highest values of the rectangle region of layer. That rectangle shape region can be determined using the input for the Max Pool Layer pool size. As instance, the layer will return the highest value in the sections of height=3 & width =2 if Pool Size = (3, 2).

3.3.6. Dropout Layers

These layers randomly and with a predetermined probability change the elements of input of layer to 0s. This procedure equates to arbitrarily removing the section and all of its network Connectivity during the learning period, despite the fact that this layer's output and input are identical. In this scenario, training of the network in an arbitrary manner for choosing a neural portion to create a distinct architecture for each new element input. Architectures with layers share weights However, the layer of dropout may aid in preventing over fitting since the training process isn't dependent on particular neuron and link types.

3.3.7. Fully Connected Layer

A single fully connected layer or a number of layers may make up these layers. After the convolutional layer, these layers are displayed. The neurons in the preceding layer are all connected to the neurons in this layer. The completely linked layer combines all learnt features from earlier layers. Larger patterns were found using these features, which were then used to classify the photos according to several categorization issues. The dataset's class numbers are output by the final fully connected layer as size arguments. The output size for regression issues must match the number of response variables.

3.3.8. Output Layers

Classification tasks are performed using the Soft Max and Classification Layers. Following the previous fully connected layer are these two layers. The Soft Max function is used in this instance to activate the output unit represent in equation 3.

$$y_r(x) = \frac{e^{a_r(x)}}{\sum_{j=1}^k e^{a_j(x)}} \quad (3)$$

where, $y_r(x)$ = softmax, $a_r(x)$ = input vector, $e^{a_r(x)}$ = input vector, k = number of classes and $e^{a_j(x)}$ = output vector

This equation displays the activation function of output unit following final completely linked layer of problems with multiclass-classification:

$$P(x, \theta) = \frac{P(c_r)P(c_r)}{\sum_{j=1}^k P(c_j)P(c_j)} = \frac{e^{a_r(x)}}{\sum_{j=1}^k e^{a_j(x)}} \quad (4)$$

The normalized exponential is another name for the soft max function represented in equation 4. Additionally, the logistic sigmoid multiclass generalization of function is being considered.

4. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

For the classification purpose of laser marks containing fundus images, the different CNN architectures with previously discussed layers and transfer functions have been used. For classification purposes, a hybrid customized system using Residual 50 and Inception v2 has been utilized. Inception-ResNet-v2 is a convolutional neural architecture that builds on the Inception family of architectures and incorporates residual connections. For the residual versions of the Inception networks, we use Inception blocks that are less expensive than those in the original Inception. Following each inception block by the layer of filter expansion, which is employed to make the filter collection more dimensional prior to being added in order to match the input's depth. It is essential to make up because of the dimensionality loss brought on utilizing the Inception block is depicted in figure 3.

FIGURE 4: Hybrid Inception-resnet-v2

For the segmentation process with mapping the masks of the segmented area of laser spots in fundus images, the residual U Net is used. The ResNet design serves as the foundation for this U-net variation. ResNet was developed with the goal of overcoming the challenges associated with training extremely deep neural networks as depicted in figure 4. It is well recognized that the more layers present in a neural network, the faster it can converge on a solution. The findings of the experiments revealed that adding more layers causes saturation, and adding more layers can result in performance reduction. This degradation is caused by the diminishing gradients of the weight vector, which lead to the loss of feature identities in deeper neural networks. ResNet lessens this problem by using skip connections to move the feature map from one layer to another deeper in the network. At each block in the network, a skip connection in the residual U-net adds the input from the first convolutional layer to the output from the second convolutional layer. Prior to any down- or up-sampling, the U-net's respective routes employ this skip connection. The vanishing gradient problem is addressed by using residual skip connections to build U-net models with deeper neural networks.

FIGURE 5: Fully Residual U net architecture [24]

Prior to adopting the suggested dataset, we conducted a fivefold cross validation to verify the randomness of the training set and testing set selection. 70 elaborately labeled photos were separated into five folds, each of which had pictures of total count 14. One of them was chosen to act as the validation set and the other 4 as training set in ensuing validation experiment. The greatest AUC value was 0.9833, and the lowest was 0.9706. Given that the range produced by these two extreme AUC values covered 0.9798, it is obvious that the initial separation of the training set and validation set was largely arbitrary. The use of stratified K fold Cross validation and ensemble learning will be helpful for this kind of separation.

After 17th epoch, the Training accuracy increased from 87 to 97%, after that it decreased to 85% and again increased from 20th epoch and stayed still to the 21st epoch. The validation accuracy is 96 % as shown in the graph.

Result	Training Accuracy of Resnet-Inception model	Validation Accuracy of Resnet-Inception model
ACCURACY	0.9877	0.9611

These hybrid architectures and entire prototype system are responsible for fast and reliable classification along with optimal segmentation task on CT scan/Fundus image analysis to identify exact location of laser spots on sensitive eye tissue. After early recognition of those sensitive spots, proper medication consultancy or mark removal surgery will take place for further treatment.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

The capacity of deep learning algorithms to be understood is AI's largest issue. A deep learning algorithm will always diagnose a fundus shot as an image with DR without presenting more, more understandable justifications for its choice. In this study, both classification and segmentation works have been done with residual based architecture. Means, inception-ResNet hybrid classification system and fully residual U-net architecture for segmentation system. We carried out a fivefold cross validation before using the suggested dataset to verify the randomness of selecting the training set and testing set. A total of 70 precisely labeled photos were used to make the five folds, which each contained 14 pictures. One of the five folds was chosen to act as the testing set in the ensuing validation experiment, while the other four served as the training set. The highest and lowest AUC values, respectively, were 0.9833 and 0.9706, respectively. The range produced by these two extreme AUC values covered 0.9798, indicating that the initial division of the training set and testing set was largely random.

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